

Electromagnetic Side-Channel Attack on a SoC-FPGA Fingerprint Recognition System

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Abstract— Biometric-as-a-Service (BaaS) recognition systems have gained widespread adoption across several sectors due to their advantages in terms of cost-efficiency, scalability and performance. In these systems, the raw fingerprint images collected by sensors are transmitted to remote nodes through secure channels. The nodes often use SoC-FPGAs to accelerate processing with hardware. Also, they incorporate advanced security measures. However, they are not very concerned about possible side-channel attacks that can retrieve biometric data at operation level. To raise awareness of this problem, this paper presents an electromagnetic (EM) side-channel attack at a PYNQ Z1 board. It is performed while the SoC-FPGA is reading the fingerprint image from the DDR3 memory. Fuzzy-logic-based rules are extracted during a training phase to explain the correlation between the electromagnetic emanations measured and the pixels transmitted. With that rule base, the attacker needs only one EM trace, acquired in 69.10 μ s or less in our experiments, to reconstruct the fingerprint image, reaching pixel-wise accuracy of 99.05%.

Keywords—Electromagnetic attack, side-channel attack, FPGA, fingerprint recognition

I. INTRODUCTION

Online identity verification has become a critical component of our digital lives. Traditional methods such as passwords, PINs or identity cards present several limitations: passwords and PINs can be shared among different people and identity cards are susceptible to loss or theft. In this scenario, biometric-based recognition systems have become increasingly popular because they are easier to use, and more difficult to steal or share. In particular, fingerprint recognition systems are one of the most widely deployed due to their convenience, ease of acquisition and reliability [1]-[2]. The major issue is the protection of biometric data, which is categorized as sensitive in the personal data protection regulations of many countries because they are persistent (cannot be changed as a password) [3].

One of the first popularized solutions for fingerprint recognition systems was so-called match-on-card systems, in which a smart card, without a sensor, receives the fingerprint

image or their extracted features (typically minutiae) from an external device and performs the comparison internally. Despite their apparent security, side-channel attacks (SCAs) were reported to extract the minutiae from these systems by exploiting their unintentional physical emissions like timing, power consumption and electromagnetic radiation [4]-[5]. SCAs are very dangerous because they are non-invasive and passive (do not interfere with the normal operation of the system or modify it), meaning they require low intrusive equipment and are stealthy and difficult to detect.

The next evolution of fingerprint recognition systems was their use in smartphones. Several Android and iOS devices provide proprietary solutions to authenticate their users by their fingerprints. Again, despite their security, electromagnetic SCAs have been reported that obtain fingerprint images from these systems [6].

More recently, Biometric-as-a-Service (BaaS) systems have gained widespread adoption across several sectors due to their advantages in terms of cost efficiency, scalability and performance [7]-[8]. In these solutions, the raw fingerprint images collected by sensors are transmitted through secure channels to remote nodes. In the nodes, biometric features can be extracted by sophisticated privacy-preserving machine learning algorithms and then stored (at registration) and compared (at verification) [9]-[10].

Big data processing in BaaS deployments has led to the widespread use of hardware accelerators in Field Programmable Gate Arrays (FPGAs). FPGAs are adopted by Cloud Service Providers (CSP), such as Microsoft, Alibaba, Amazon and Huawei [11]. The security of these solutions is improved by using not only adequate cryptography [9]-[10] but also hardware/software architectures. Concerning the latter, Trusted Execution Environments (TEEs), such as ARM TrustZone, are employed in FPGA-based SoCs (Systems on Chips) like the Zynq-7000 from AMD/Xilinx, because they integrate ARM processors with programmable logic. Several side-channel attacks have been reported at these systems, like the cache timing-based SCA presented in [12]. These attacks often aim at recovering keys from cryptographic systems (for example, the full key of an AES software implementation in the case of [12]). However, no SCA based on electromagnetic radiation has been reported to BaaS systems, to the best of authors' knowledge.

In this work, we present a novel electromagnetic (EM) SCA to a BaaS fingerprint recognition system. The remote node uses a SoC-FPGA to accelerate the processing of the fingerprint images. In particular, during the feature extraction steps, the images are temporarily stored in memory and then read by the SoC-FPGA. The attack targets the memory controller of the SoC-FPGA during the transfer of the

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fingerprint image to the hardware accelerator where feature extraction occurs.

Importantly, our results show that short periods of unprotected storage can expose sensitive biometric data. While encryption or obfuscation are well-known countermeasures, they may be overlooked or inconsistently applied in practice. This reinforces the need for hardware-level protections to ensure that fingerprint images are never available in clear form, even temporarily.

The attack is demonstrated with a PYNQ Z1 board whose main components analyzed are a Zynq-7000 SoC-FPGA and a DDR3 (Dual-Data Rate) memory.

The main contributions of this work are:

- We demonstrate that fingerprint images can be reconstructed by analyzing the electromagnetic emissions from the DDR3 memory controller of the SoC-FPGA, without requiring knowledge of the hardware acceleration implemented in the programmable logic.
- Since the electromagnetic emanations are fuzzy, we present a fuzzy-logic-based algorithm to reconstruct the fingerprint images, whose rules are obtained from the knowledge extracted from multiple EM traces corresponding to random black and white images. The algorithm reconstructs fingerprint images with high accuracy (over 95%) using only a single EM trace in the attack phase.

The paper is structured as follows. Section II reviews the related work. The assumptions of the proposed attack are given in Section III. The hardware setup employed is described in Section IV. Section V presents the proposed fuzzy-logic-based attack. Section VI discusses the main results obtained. Finally, conclusions are given in Section VII.

II. RELATED WORK

SCAs in biometric recognition systems are not extensively explored. In fact, in 2020, [13] provided a comprehensive review of SCAs in biometric systems highlighting the lack of research in this topic. From 2020 to the current date, there have not been many advancements in this research line. For fingerprint-based recognition systems, SCAs have been applied to match-on-card or smartphone-centralized approaches. The most significant works related to this are described in the following.

Chouta et al. [4] present a practical example performing a SCA on an embedded fingerprint matcher in smart cards. In order to recover a complete fingerprint, it requires about 51.200 traces and to control the input of the feature extractor. Also, this approach demands significant computational processing time, reaching several hours per minutiae even on high-performance computers. Although they demonstrate the technical feasibility of the attack, the high computational cost and data acquisition requirements highlight the practical limitations of these attacks in real-world scenarios.

Dürmuth et al. [5] also demonstrate how fingerprint matching algorithms are vulnerable to side-channel attacks through electromagnetic analysis. Their approach also involves sending controlled minutiae inputs to the system and observing electromagnetic leakage patterns to determine when matches occur with the stored templates. Their minutiae

guessing is much more efficient than [4] since it reduces the necessary traces to a few tens. While the attack successfully recovers a pool of stored minutiae, it cannot associate which minutiae belongs to specific fingerprints in multi-template systems.

Ni et al. [6] demonstrate an attack against in-display fingerprint sensors in smartphones by exploiting electromagnetic side-channel leakage. Their attack is performed whenever the fingerprint images are acquired and the smartphone is being charged. A specific system, FPLlogger, is presented that captures EM emanations during authentication using a modified wireless charging power bank, then employed adaptive signal processing and deep learning to reconstruct actual fingerprint images with up to 75% similarity to the originals. Using these reconstructed images, they created 3D fingerprint models that successfully spoofed five different smartphone models with a 54% success rate.

The attacks in [4] and [5] require access to the user smart cards while they are performing recognition, which we consider that is difficult to carry out without the individual noticing. In contrast, in our attack the user does not realize that their biometric data is being stolen. In addition, it is possible the collection of biometrics from multiple users within the same attack. The attacker in [4] and [5] should have knowledge of the matching algorithm, which we consider as a drawback since, currently, many biometric algorithms are proprietary. We also consider a drawback that the attacker in [6] requires the use of a modified wireless charging power bank.

III. ATTACK ASSUMPTIONS

In the context of BaaS systems, we consider a typical architecture composed of a sensor at the user side, which acquires the fingerprint image, and a remote node provided with a SoC-FPGA to which the image arrives through a secure channel and where the feature extraction is performed. We assume the following concerning the attacker knowledge and capability.

Attacker Knowledge: The attacker needs to know which SoC-FPGA and DDR3 memory are employed in the system and a basic understanding of how the DDR3 memory controller works at the SoC FPGA. No knowledge of the software running on the processing system or the hardware implemented in the programmable logic of the FPGA is necessary, as the attack relies solely on observing electromagnetic emanation during data transfers. The image size can be inferred by analyzing the EM signal temporal structure, as will be shown in the following section. These are considered advantages of our attack.

Attacker Capability: The attacker must collect EM traces while the SoC-FPGA is reading image data from the DDR3 memory. At a training phase, while adjusting the fuzzy-logic-based algorithm employed in the attack, images with random black and white pixels are employed. Importantly, the training and attack phases do not need to be performed on the same physical device. In our experiments, the attack algorithm was trained using EM traces acquired from one FPGA board and successfully applied to attack other boards of the same model. This demonstrates that the attack methodology is robust across different instances of the same hardware platform. This characteristic significantly increases the practicality of the proposed attack: an adversary may prepare the attack

Fig. 1. Experimental setup of the attack.

algorithm using a development board identical to the target without requiring access to the actual target during training. Once the algorithm is defined, the attacker must have access to the SoC FPGA in the remote node and take a single trace of the fingerprint image transference between the DDR3 memory and the SoC-FPGA.

IV. HARDWARE SETUP

Our attack has been carried out using a PYNQ Z1 board as the board at the remote node side. It has a 512 MB DDR3 memory and a Zynq-7000 SoC-FPGA with the following components: 650 MHz dual-core Cortex-A9 processor, DDR3 memory controller with 8 DMA channels and 4 high performance AXI3 slave ports, high and low bandwidth peripheral controllers, and programmable logic equivalent to Artix-7 FPGA. The DDR3 controller uses a 16-bit data bus, which means data is transferred in pairs of bytes simultaneously.

The system attacked consists of a hardware accelerator implemented in the programmable logic of the SoC-FPGA through the FINN library. It performs a neural network that processes input images stored in the PYNQ-Z1 DDR3 memory.

The hardware equipment employed in the attack is the following:

- An oscilloscope: Agilent DSO81304B Infiniium, with 13 GHz, 4 analog channels, and up to 40 Gsa/s.
- A field probe: H field probe RF-R 3-2 from Langer RF1 set, with 30 MHz to 3 GHz, 3 mm diameter, and sensitive at very short distances.
- A pre-amplifier: the Rohde & Schwarz Pre-amplifier HZ-16 (3 GHz).

The experimental setup is shown in Fig. 1.

A. Location test

For the location of the best position for the probe, we explored the EM emanations of the SoC-FPGA to locate the

Fig. 2. Synchronization of data sending with the capture.

Fig. 3. Zoon in Fig 2.

zones presenting notable EM leakage during data transfer. We detected that the electromagnetic field patterns observed during transmission correspond to the signed Hamming distance between consecutive byte pairs. This is because working at dual rate, 4 bytes are transmitted in a clock cycle: 2 bytes first and 2 bytes second. Assuming that bytes are image pixels and that they can be black or white, the electromagnetic patterns observed correspond to the possible transitions between pairs of pixels as they are read from the memory. A black pixel is a byte with the value 0 and a white pixel is a byte with the value 255. Hence, we observed 9 possible changes between the pairs in a clock cycle as follows: [+255 0], [+255 +255], [0 0], [-255 -255], [0 +255], [+255 -255], [0 -255], [-255 +255], and [-255 0]. For example, a change [+255 0] means that the first byte changed from 0 to 255 and the second byte remained the same.

The data activity was measured when substantial peaks appeared. For example, we sent a 28x28 pixel image (784 bytes). We set to 0 the first 380 bytes and the last 376 bytes, and the other 28 bytes were set to the patterns of 4 bytes (255, 255, 0, 0), (255, 255, 0, 0) repeated 7 times. These patterns correspond to the changes [-255 -255] and [+255 +255], with the greatest Hamming distance among the possible changes, making them easier to detect.

These results (shown in Fig. 2 and Fig. 3) allowed us to find the correct placement of the probe on the SoC-FPGA and to draw the conclusion that the leakage came from the DDR3 memory controller.

B. Synchronization test

The leakage pattern allowed us to obtain information about the data transfers because the traces could be conveniently timed to identify the exact part of the trace that was correlated with the transmitted data. What is seen at the beginning and at the end of the trace in Fig. 2 is the hand-shake protocol between the memory and the controller, which in [15] is called pre-amble and post-amble. The cursors in Fig. 2, which are placed at the beginning and at the end of the data trace, indicate that the data (784 bytes) are sent in 373 ns. This is in accordance with the frequency of the transfers between the DDR3 memory and the SoC-FPGA (525 MHz) and that 4 bytes are sent on each clock cycle, because of the double data rate of the memory.

V. FUZZY-LOGIC-BASED ATTACK

To design the attack algorithm, the electromagnetic emanations from the memory controller during image data transfers were analyzed. We measured at the oscilloscope the amplitudes that characterize each change. The procedure to

Fig. 4. Probability density functions of changes produced in even positions.

analyze these amplitudes and define the attack algorithm was as follows.

A. Estimating the probability density functions of the byte changes

As previously established, the electromagnetic signals observed are correlated to the signed Hamming distances between consecutive byte pairs. Due to the dual data rate of the DDR3 communication, two bytes are sent during the high level and another two during the low level of the clock signal. This creates a distinction between "even" and "odd" positions in the transmitted data sequence, resulting in 18 total possible changes that can be identified: 9 for even positions and 9 for odd positions.

To characterize these changes, we measured the peak voltage amplitudes produced by each possible transition in 80 training traces obtained when transmitting images with random black and white pixels. The training was performed using truly random black and white images to ensure all possible byte pair transitions are covered with equal probability, enabling the system to detect any transition pattern that may occur in real fingerprint images. Our analysis revealed that each change can be modeled by a Gaussian distribution. Fig. 4 shows the probability density functions (PDFs) corresponding to the possible 9 changes occurring at even positions.

While these distributions may appear overlapped, not all changes are accessible from any given byte pair. For instance,

Fig. 5. PDFs of accessible changes from the bytes [255 255] at an even position.

Fig. 6. Membership functions of the 4 fuzzy sets correlated to the changes from the bytes [255 255] at even positions.

from the byte pair [255 255], only 4 specific transitions are possible. Fig. 5 illustrates the PDFs of the accessible changes from [255 255] at even positions.

B. Representing byte-pair changes as fuzzy sets of amplitude values

Once the probability density functions commented above were modelled and a byte-pair i is assumed to be transmitted at the high or low level of the clock signal, we propose to represent the possible changes (odd and even) that the byte-pair i can experience as fuzzy sets, because the changes have uncertainty. Then, we define the membership degree of a given voltage amplitude to a fuzzy set correlated to a specific change j from a byte-pair i at k level (odd and even) as follows:

$$\mu(\text{amplitude})_{ij}^k = \frac{PDF(\text{amplitude})_{ij}^k}{\sum_{j=1}^4 PDF(\text{amplitude})_{ij}^k} \quad (1)$$

where PDF_{ij}^k is the probability density function associated with the change j from the byte-pair i at k level of the clock.

If we plot these membership functions for each change, considering only the range $\mu \pm 5\sigma$ as different from 0 in the PDFs, we obtain Fig. 6 for the changes from bytes [255 255] at even positions. The membership functions represented in Fig. 6 from the left to the right represent fuzzy sets that can be named as *very negative*, *negative*, *slightly negative* and *positive*. We can observe that, in certain voltage intervals, the degree of membership is equal to 1, indicating that for those peak amplitude values, the occurrence of a specific transition is fully certain. Since there are 4 possible byte-pairs and 4 possible changes from each depending on the amplitude, this translates to 16 possible combinations. If we consider the need to differentiate between pairs of bytes in even and odd positions, we obtain 32 fuzzy rules that explain linguistically the correlation between the electromagnetic emanations measured and the byte-pair changes produced. Examples of these rules associated to the fuzzy sets in Fig. 6 are the following:

R1: IF the peak amplitude measured is *very negative* AND previous_byte_pair is [255, 255] AND position is even THEN change is [-255, -255]

R2: IF the peak amplitude measured is *negative* AND previous_byte_pair is [255, 255] AND position is even THEN change is [0, -255]

C. The attack algorithm

To successfully reconstruct the data processed by the DDR3 memory controller at the SoC-FPGA, our proposal is that the attacker executes the steps summarized in Algorithm 1, which generates a black and white image by associating the changes with higher certainty to the peak amplitude voltages observed in the EM collected trace. The acquired trace needs to be preprocessed and sampled according to the number of byte pairs in the transferred data knowing that one byte-pair is sent every 0.95 ns (the 525-MHz frequency of the transfers between the DDR3 memory and the SoC-FPGA).

The first byte pair is obtained by analyzing the preamble pattern (which is different for each byte pair). This is done in Algorithm 1 by using the function *analyze_preamble_pattern*.

Using the fuzzy-logic-based rules described above, the attacker calculates the certainty of the changes as the activation degree of the rules (which are equal to the membership degrees of the peak amplitude voltages to the correlated fuzzy sets). The function *obtain_changes* in Algorithm 1 returns these potential changes with their certainty degrees. As the attacker advances over the measured peak amplitudes associated to a potential change in the pair of bytes (increasing the variable *index*), the possible changes per byte are calculated with their degrees of certainty. Then, the change is selected by using the function *select_change* and it is applied to the next pair by using the function

Algorithm 1: reconstruct transmitted image

```

Input: amplitudes
Output: trial_byte_pairs
1  global initial_pair ← analyze_preamble_pattern()
2  global trial_byte_pairs = [initial_pair]
3  global index = 2
4  global tried_changes = []
5  while index < length(amplitudes) do
6    [changes, certainty_degrees]
    ← obtain_changes(trial_byte_pairs[index-1],
    amplitudes[index])
7    while all certainty_degrees are zero do
8      index = index - 1
9      if index < 2 return error
10     end if
11     [changes, certainty_degrees]
    ← obtain_changes(trial_byte_pairs[index-1],
    amplitudes[index])
12    end while
13    selected_change ← select_change(changes,
    certainty_degrees)
14    tried_changes = [tried_changes, selected_change]
15    next_pair ← apply_selected_change(selected_change,
    trial_byte_pairs[index-1])
16    index = index + 1
17    trial_byte_pairs = [trial_byte_pairs, next_pair]
18  end while

```

Function: select_change

```

Input: changes, certainty_degrees
Output: selected_change
1  for changes do
2    if tried_changes(index) is empty do
3      selected_change ← fuzzy_selection(changes,
    certainty_degrees)
4    else do
5      selected_change ← select_change_not_in_tried_changes(changes)
6    end if
7  end for

```

Fig. 7. Comparison between the original image (left) and the reconstructed image (right) of a fingerprint acquired with an optical sensor.

apply_selected_change. The selected changes are stored in the variable *tried_changes*.

Since the employed rules to select the changes are fuzzy, it may happen at some iterations that all the certainty degrees obtained are zero. Since this is not accepted, the algorithm applies backtracking and decreases the variable *index*. If no backtracking is done, the function *select_change* performs a fuzzy choice of a certain change according to its degree of certainty by using the function *fuzzy_selection*. The change with the highest certainty degree is selected.

When backtracking, the function *select_change_not_in_tried_changes* selects the next change in the ranking of the selection that was not selected in the first exploration.

VI. RESULTS

To validate the effectiveness of the proposed attack, the algorithm presented in the previous section was first tested on electromagnetic traces obtained from the transfer of random black and white images that were not used during the training phase. These test traces represent high-entropy images with uniformly distributed black and white pixels. The average reconstruction accuracy, measured as the percentage of correctly recovered pixels, reached 97.28%, confirming the attack's ability to generalize to unseen data. Furthermore, the average number of iterations required to reconstruct the image was $1.01 \cdot (N/2 - 1)$, and the minimum number of iterations was $(N/2 - 1)$, N being the number of pixels of the image. This demonstrates the computational efficiency of the attack, which means that the attack is very fast.

To assess the attack robustness across different physical instances of the hardware, additional EM traces were captured during image transfers on two PYNQ-Z1 boards distinct from the one used during training. The model, trained on a single board, achieved an average reconstruction accuracy of 92.2% and 97.36% on these additional devices, with an average of $1.04 \cdot (N/2 - 1)$ and $1.03 \cdot (N/2 - 1)$ iterations, respectively. These results confirm that the attack methodology is generalizable across different boards of the same model.

Having confirmed the effectiveness of the model on high-entropy data, we then evaluated its performance on actual black-and-white fingerprint images transmitted through the DDR3 memory controller. The images used for validation are those from the FVC2002-Db1-a and FCV2000-Db2-a databases [16]-[17]. These fingerprint images were acquired with optical and capacitive sensors, respectively. Fig. 7 and Fig. 8 show two examples of the fingerprint images

Fig. 8. Comparison between the original image (left) and the reconstructed image (right) of a fingerprint acquired with a capacitive sensor.

reconstructed. The pixel-wise accuracies are 99.05% and 96.50%, respectively, with visual results showing a near-exact reproduction of the ridge patterns. The reconstructions were obtained using only a single EM trace per image. Since the images from the FVC2002-Db1-a and FCV2000-Db2-a databases have 388*374 and 256*364 pixels, they are transferred from the DDR3 memory to the SoC-FPGA in 69.10 μ s and 44.37 μ s, respectively. This is the time the attacker needs to acquire the EM trace.

Using the fuzzy-logic-based attack, the attacker can also evaluate the average occurrences of the 9 possible changes in the reconstructed images, which are correlated with the entropy of the images. Table I shows these percentages for the fingerprint images analyzed. The asymmetry in these occurrence percentages is due to the fact that fingerprint images are not random.

VII. CONCLUSIONS

This work demonstrates a practical electromagnetic side-channel attack capable of reconstructing raw fingerprint images transmitted from the DDR3 memory to the SoC-FPGA in a PYNQ Z1 board. The attacker does not need knowledge of the software running on the processing system or the hardware implemented in the programmable logic of the SoC-FPGA but only a basic understanding of how the DDR3 memory controller works at the SoC-FPGA.

The fuzzy-logic-based rules extracted from traces corresponding to high-entropy black and white images during a training phase, generalizes effectively to reconstruct real fingerprint images during the attack phase. Also, we have checked that the rule base generalizes across different PYNQ Z1 boards, making the attack feasible in real-world scenarios where the attacker does not have access to the remote nodes during the training phase. The attack also requires a minimal number of iterations, highlighting its computational efficiency.

Given the increasing deployment of BaaS systems, this work exposes a serious privacy threat: attackers can extract sensitive biometric data very fast and in a manner difficult to be detected since the attack is passive and non-invasive. The results underscore the need to develop and adopt countermeasures to prevent side-channel attacks in these systems.

TABLE I. OCCURRENCE OF CHANGES (IN %) IN THE FINGERPRINT IMAGES ANALYZED

-255, -255	-255, 0	-255, +255	0, -255	0, 0	0, +255	+255, -255	+255, 0	+255, +255
6.3%	6.1%	0.3%	6.3%	62.0%	6.2%	0.1%	6.4%	6.2%

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